

IMPROVING E-GOVERNMENT THROUGH SENTIMENT ANALYSIS IN THE CONTEXT OF DEVELOPING COUNTRIES: A MAURITANIA CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

New technologies have given rise to online platforms such as Facebook and X (formerly Twitter), which have become de facto channels of communication, enabling people to express their opinions in writing. Analyzing the user-generated data makes it possible to identify opinions and sentiments on specific topics, thereby providing valuable insights for evidence-based decision-making. Therefore, this study focuses on the HASSANIYA dialect, a low-resource variety of Arabic, and proposes a sentiment classification system based on Natural Language Processing (NLP) to support decision-making. In the first step, A dedicated dataset was collected from Facebook, preprocessed using a combination of a Hassaniya-specific stemmer and an Arabic stemmer. Then, different configurations of feature extraction (n-grams) and weighting (TF-IDF) were applied to construct effective feature representations and determine the best classification model. Support Vector Machines (SVM), Logistic Regression (LR), and Random Forest (RF) were used to classify the HASSANIYA dataset. The proposed approach was designed to analyze comments written in both Modern Standard Arabic (MSA) and the HASSANIYA dialect on Facebook and Twitter. The results show that SVM achieved the best performance and was successfully validated through a real case study involving the classification of comments from an X account (Twitter). Finally, this study introduces a prototype dashboard for visualizing sentiment trends, offering a practical tool to support e-government strategies in Mauritania.

Keywords: *Sentiment Analysis, NLP, Feature Extraction, Decision-Making, e-Government, Social Media, HASSANIYA Dialect, Machine Learning Algorithms*

1. INTRODUCTION

Sentiment analysis (SA) is a computational method used to identify the sentiment or opinion expressed in a text and to provide an overview of public attitudes toward specific topics [1]. At the sentence level, the process begins by determining if the sentence is subjective or objective [2]. Two principal approaches to sentiment analysis are commonly used: The first is a lexicon-based approach, which uses a collection of predefined words, each annotated according to whether it represents a positive, negative, or neutral sentiment [3]. This approach is used to extract, interpret, and

determine opinions from a text [4]. The second is a machine-learning based approach [5], which classifies texts using supervised [6] or unsupervised [7] learning techniques.

Recently, due to the technology that has emerged, social media has become widely used by citizens around the world [8]. In Mauritania in particular, the number of social media users has increased to more than 25% of the total population¹; Consequently, a continuous stream of data is being generated, reflecting citizens' information or opinions on published actions, while governors have a crucial need to know citizens' reactions, enabling them to improve their services and review the need for their

¹<https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2024-mauritania?rq=mauritania>

overall strategy. When making decisions, governors should take into account the opinions of all or the majority of citizens, without ignoring those who expressed their views through social media. This is where the concept of e-government began, which emerged in the late 1990s [9]. Also referred to as *electronic government*, *digital government*, or *electronic governance*, it is defined according to [10] as the use of the Web and the information and telecommunications technologies to provide government services to citizens. E-government presents a key factor for improving government services and the effectiveness of public policy strategy [11].

This study investigates sentiment analysis of the Mauritanian dialect ‘HASSANIYA’ using a supervised machine learning approach. Several preprocessing techniques were applied, including stop-words removal based on a combined list of Standard Arabic and HASSANIYA-specific terms, as well as stemming carried out with Arabic stemmers enhanced with rules adapted to HASSANIYA, in order to process the collected comments. We also experimented with different feature extraction methods, such as n-grams and weighting schemes like TF-IDF, to construct effective feature representations for classification Models. In addition, we evaluated several machine learning algorithms, such as Support Vector Machines (SVM), Random Forests (RF), and Logistic Regression (LR), to classify comments and tweets according to their sentiment.

The proposed model is designed as a tool to improve the effectiveness of e-government by applying sentiment analysis to social media content, particularly in the HASSANIYA dialect, and by enhancing models’ performance by combining machine-learning algorithms with optimized feature-extraction techniques. This methodology strengthens the ability to process dialectal text and improves sentiment classification accuracy. The best-performing model also serves as the basis for a prototype dashboard that supports government decision-makers by analyzing citizens’ feedback on official content.

The main contributions of this study are as follows:

- Proposing a comprehensive set of preprocessing techniques tailored to the HASSANIYA dialect, specifically designed to address its morphological complexity.
- Extracting and selecting features (individual words or word groups) from Facebook

comments improve sentiment classification performance.

- Identifying the most effective model for predicting citizen sentiment and developing a government-oriented dashboard that categorizes comments by sentiment to support better decision-making and strengthen the Government-to-Citizen (G2C) relationship.

By focusing on HASSANIYA, this work contributes to filling an important research gap in Arabic NLP and demonstrates how sentiment analysis can serve as a practical tool for supporting e-government initiatives in Mauritania. The study is guided by the hypothesis that applying machine learning (ML) and natural language processing (NLP) techniques to the HASSANIYA dialect can effectively identify public sentiment and provide valuable insights to improve the effectiveness of e-government.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the background of the study, including the basic concepts and related work on sentiment analysis in Arabic and its dialects. Section 3 introduces the case study and outlines the main challenges in the research context. Section 4 describes the proposed approach in detail, while Section 5 discusses the experimental findings. Section 6 concludes this paper.

2. BACKGROUND

In this section, we respectively describe the basic concepts on which this study is based, followed by an overview of existing studies on Arabic and its dialectal texts’ classification, with a particular focus on the Arab Maghreb sub-region.

2.1. Basic Concepts

- *Natural Language Processing (NLP)*: is the intersection between computational linguistics and computer science, it appeared in the 1950s [12]. NLP is defined as a technique allowing computers to understand, generate, and manipulate human language.
- *Sentiment Analysis (SA)*: According to [7], SA is an interdisciplinary field between natural language processing [13] and machine learning [14][15], or lexicon-based methods [3]. SA is interested in the extraction, conversion, interpretation, and determination of opinions from text [4]; And classifying them into positive, negative or neutral sentiments.

- *E-government*: The use of information and communication technologies (ICT) to support government business strategy, and improve public sector activities. According to [10] e-gov is defined as the use of ICT and the World Wide Web to provide government information and services to citizens
- *Social media*: These are exchange platforms that have recently emerged thanks to new technologies, which consider the Internet as a communication channel and enable inter-family and inter-governmental ex-changes, as well as bilateral exchanges between government agencies and the public (citizens), according to [16]. In this sense, it seems to underline that social media represents an important means of developing and maintaining the G2C relationship.

2.2. Related Work

This subsection reviews studies on Arabic dialects from neighboring sub-regions, with particular attention to recent approaches based on machine learning and transformer models. It also outlines research related to government services and citizen engagement, thereby situating the role of sentiment analysis within the broader context of e-government initiatives.

This paper [17] presented a methodology for sentiment analysis on social media using advanced deep learning approaches. It addressed data collection and preprocessing, feature extraction (TF-IDF, Word2Vec, GloVe), and model optimization (BiLSTM variants, GridSearchCV). Experimental results demonstrated that the proposed framework outperformed comparative methods, providing robust and generalizable solutions for real-world sentiment analysis applications. An approach conducted by [18] focused on sentiment analysis in Arabic Morocco, taking advantage of pre-trained models, namely: ALBERT, AraELACTRA, AraBERT, QARIB, and CAMeLBERT. These models were integrated into ML and DL models (SVM, CNN). In addition to the fine-tuning of the pre-trained models, the study examined the impact of the count vectorizer through evaluation on three datasets. The results demonstrated that BERT-based models achieved better performance compared to when combined with CNN or SVM, marking a significant advancement in Moroccan Arabic sentiment analysis. Another study [19] introduced a framework for analyzing Twitter reviews that aids marketers and consumers in decision-making. The system

design combined a lexical sentiment analysis tool and machine learning, enabling marketers to interpret qualitative user-generated content and transform it into quantitative representations. An Algerian research team aimed to perform sentiment analysis on the Algerian dialect using the BERT model. They collected and annotated a dataset from YouTube and applied BERT, achieving an F-score of 78.38% on the test set [20]. A Moroccan dialect classification model using a dataset collected from Twitter comments was proposed by [21]. They applied word embeddings, weighting schemes (BoW, TF-IDF), and n-gram features, alongside various machine learning algorithms (Naive Bayes, Random Forest, SVM, Logistic Regression, and LSTM). Experimental results showed that SVM achieved the highest accuracy of 70%. This paper [22] focused on the Serbian language and presented a solution based on the statistical n-grams method to classify unstructured Serbian text. The model was trained on datasets scraped from a news portal using hyperparameters such as 3–5 letter n-grams, document vector reduction, and vector length.

An empirical study [23] employed transformer-based language models to extract relevant insights into citizens' interests, sentiments, and emotions toward public services. Similarly, this study [24] aimed to develop a sentiment analysis-based model to engage the public in governance in Kenya. Using the BERT transformer model to detect user sentiment, the study resulted in a mobile application that enabled citizen participation in national activities and influenced development progress. This work of [25] introduced MASR, a corpus of 2,469 Egyptian Arabic mobile-app reviews, evaluated classical machine learning classifiers (KNN, SVM, LR, RF) and a deep learning model (MLP), and proposed a hybrid supervised classifier that combines the best-performing ML models with the MLP, achieving improved sentiment classification performance. A survey on Business Intelligence (BI) for e-government in Mauritania was presented by [15], which reviewed existing BI works in support of e-government and suggested directions for improving public services. The study in [26] investigated the effectiveness of several machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) models for Twitter sentiment analysis, aiming to classify tweets as positive, negative, or neutral. The methodology included preprocessing and feature extraction using TF-IDF and BERT embeddings. The evaluated models include Naive Bayes (MNB and CNB), SVM (linear and RBF), and BiLSTM. Results showed that RBF-SVM performed

best among ML models with 88.64% accuracy, while BiLSTM achieved 87.72%.

To the best of our knowledge, [14] represented the first attempt to study HASSANIYA dialect text extracted from Facebook comments. The authors used a Naive Gaussian Bayesian classifier and created a dashboard for the Mauritanian government to classify and visualize comments by polarity. An approach based on NLP to investigate the impact of various preprocessing techniques on sentiment classification was proposed by [27]. The authors trained supervised learning and lexicon-based models on three Tunisian datasets of positive and negative tweets and comments. Results showed that preprocessing steps such as stemming, emoji recognition, and negation detection significantly improved classification performance. This paper [28] provided a comprehensive review of advances in applying deep learning to sentiment analysis. The authors demonstrated that deep approaches (embeddings, CNN, RNN, LSTM, recursive networks) significantly outperformed traditional methods such as BoW, TF-IDF, and lexicons by capturing semantics and context more effectively. They highlighted applications in text classification, opinion mining, and sentiment lexicon construction, and concluded that deep learning represents a promising direction for sentiment analysis.

Building upon our previous studies [14][15], which successively introduced the first HASSANIYA sentiment analysis prototype, investigated the impact of stemming on Mauritanian dialect classification, and examined n-gram feature extraction effects, the present work consolidates and extends this research. It enlarges the dataset with additional social media comments, integrates optimized preprocessing combining Hassaniya-specific stemming and TF-IDF n-grams, and evaluates multiple machine learning algorithms in a real e-government context. Ultimately, the novelty of this study lies in its ability to support decision-makers by enabling data-driven insights that accurately reflect citizens' perceptions.

3. CASE STUDY DESCRIPTION

3.1 Context and Problem Statement

Sentiment analysis applied to social media data streams represents a major challenge in the field of Business Intelligence (BI). Social media platforms generate vast amounts of user-generated content that

reflect public opinion on a wide range of issues, providing an opportunity for governments and organizations to capture and analyze citizens' perceptions in real time. In the Mauritanian context, according to the National Digital Department², the government has launched more than 100 online services, and each ministry, as well as every directorate, maintains an official Facebook page.

Previous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of machine learning and deep learning approaches for sentiment classification in several Arabic dialects, including Egyptian, Moroccan [18], and Algerian Arabic [25]. However, few studies have addressed the HASSANIYA dialect [14][15]. This lack of research limits the potential for developing tools that could help local governments monitor and understand public opinion in Mauritania.

This study aims to address these gaps by focusing on the main issues:

- *Sentiment analysis of the HASSANIYA Dialect:* Some text classification algorithms depend on the context of the word in the sentence to which they belong. Previous works have studied the composition of the phases (Morphology), as well as the contexts (Syntactic, Semantic) of the HASSANIYA sentence, which is completely different from the Latin languages, and also investigated the effect of which stemmer on the HASSANIYA dialect; Analysis experiments will be applied to dialect corpora in order to get out of them and adopt the best technology to remove affixes for dialectal text classification;
- *Storage of unnecessary data:* Storing this data before being analyzed has negative aspects such as increasing the quantities stored, which can delay or even damage the analysis process; thus, delaying decision-making. To overcome this challenge, in real-time or live analysis process from the data stream should be implemented using ELT (Extract, Load, Transform) or similar streaming approaches;
- *Decision-making:* With the technological transformation, BI Batch has become outdated, because we need to react immediately to citizens' expectations and make appropriate decisions. Which was not answered by the BI batch.

3.2 HASSANIYA dialect Description

HASSANIYA is a variety of Modern Standard Arabic (MSA) that uses the same letters of the Arabic alphabet, written from right to left. However,

² <https://mtnima.gov.mr/fr/strategies-et-politiques/>

its pronunciation and meaning change depending on diacritics and context; like MSA, the HASSANIYA dialect has affixes; for instance, خَلَيْتُو that means "I let it", the root of this word is 'خَلَى', and 'تُو' indicates as a suffix. Moreover, it is a local dialect spoken by Mauritanian Arabs, who are about 80% of the total population, widely used in their daily life to exchange between family members, express or share feelings and opinions on social media, and interact with other people's posts. And closely resembles the dialect of the Maghreb sub-regions.

Related to Mauritanian regions, four types of HASSANIYA dialect have been distinguished and described by [29], such as ahl sharg (east), ahl ssaahil(west), ahl itel(north), and ahl gibla(south), among which people have these particular senses of words rather than their morphology; here it is important to emphasize that this diversity presents one of the complexities of the HASSANIYA dialect.

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الدور موقع اللجنة المنظمة للانتخابات ,neutre
عُتِدن الانتخابات تركيا مان مايبين الكم ,negative
ايكد مايتحكيم ,negative
ماكاينن اقباهم اليوم امورين لعب مكشوف ,negative
الانتخابات ماه ففاه ايذا وتظالم الجمهور بتصويت لي فخصيا ,negative
ماينن اندوره زين اخياره من اعلام غيرتم ,negative
إهتتن الص ذلك لإيولنه ,negative
نظمة ظيلائها عفرة ,negative
زعزعة الأمن القومي أنتم ,negative
لا اتلات اتورطكم النتائج الكل حمل عليها إلا أنتم ,negative
مكنت موريتانيا احسن تمثيل جزاها في عنا خيرا ,positive
مكذا أدت و قامت بما تديها الفرع الإسلامي إليه ,positive
تقبل في منها في ينصر إسلام في جميع البلدان ,positive
    
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Figure 1: Example of the HASSANIYA Dialect text

4. PROPOSED METHOD

This section describes the experimental methodology adopted for sentiment classification of the Mauritanian dialect 'HASSANIYA'. The implementation relies on the Scikit-learn library and follows a supervised machine learning. The overall workflow is summarized in Figure 2, includes four main phases. First, social media comments in the HASSANIYA dialect were collected and manually annotated to create a labeled dataset. Second, the texts were preprocessed to remove noise, normalize characters, and apply customized stop-words removal and stemming. Third, the processed data were transformed into numerical vectors using n-gram and TF-IDF techniques for model training. Finally, the models were evaluated using standard performance metrics, and the best-performing one was validated through a real case study, confirming the main research hypothesis. The following subsections describe each phase in detail.

Figure 2 presents the conceptual framework and process of the proposed sentiment-analysis system. The framework connects social media data collection, preprocessing, sentiment classification, and dashboard visualization, showing how citizens' opinions are transformed into actionable insights for e-government decision-making.

Figure 2: Process of Sentiment analysis system

4.1. Data Collection

The dataset used in this study comprises 1,851 sentences from Facebook comments on government services and political discourse, focusing on Mauritania's 2024 presidential election. Data were collected via web scraping and annotated with Label Studio, with each comment labeled as positive, negative, or neutral. To the best of our knowledge, this dataset represents the first publicly available dataset in this dialect. It combines a manually curated subset and comments extracted from relevant Facebook pages. collected exclusively from public pages in compliance with Facebook's API policy [30]. Annotation quality was ensured through independent review by two native Arabic speakers. The dataset is divided into three sentiment classes, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of sentiment labels in the dataset

Sentiment Label	Count
Positive	695
Negative	643
Neutral	513

4.2. Data Preprocessing

Preprocessing is an important step in preparing data for analysis and also, has a major impact on the

where words are reduced to their roots. The process begins with the initialization of removable affixes of dialectal words through the function *InitializeRules()*. Then, the function *stem_word(word)* is defined to iterate over the tokenized corpus, processing each token individually. During this processing phase, the function removes or replaces affixes with their corresponding substitutions and finally returns the stemmed word.

sentiment	text	tokens	stemmed_text
Neutral	أهوه	[أهوه]	ه
Negative	شبهاني العجل يثبير	[شبهاني العجل يثبير]	شبهان العجل يثبير
Positive	السلام عليكم ورحمة الله وبركاته	[السلام عليكم ورحمة الله وبركاته]	سلام عليكم ورحم وبركات
Negative	الله محترم يراجع	[الله محترم يراجع]	الله محترم يراجع
Positive	زين	[زين]	زين
...
Positive	ماذا طاهر ممتاز بالخص الامر اجيدني	[ماذا طاهر ممتاز بالخص الامر اجيدني]	ماذا طاهر ممتاز بالخص الامر اجيدني
Positive	يتروق الجميلات شاداه	[يتروق الجميلات ما شاداه]	يتروق جميلة شاداه
Negative	عاده بيت التسيه	[عوه عاده ر بيت التسيه]	عاده بيت التسيه
Positive	فهم وحدة خاس عليها	[فهم وحدة ما خاسر عليها شي]	فهم وحد خاس عليه
Positive	مناظرنا زاهر ابروفسين	[مناظرنا زاهر ابروفسين]	مناظرنا زاهر ابروفسين

Figure 3: Tokenized and stemmed texts

Figure 3 shows part of the dataset after the preprocessing steps indicated in the second column, with tokenized and stemmed texts represented in the third column.

4.3. Text Representation

The text presentation techniques used in this study are as follows:

- N-gram is a fundamental concept in NLP, and an important feature in text classification and sentiment analysis, capturing meaningful patterns that contribute to the characterization of different classes or sentiments. In the context of NLP, N-grams usually presents a sequence of N items that can be words, characters, or even syllables [35, 33]; In the same context, N-grams can help us capture contextual information and semantics in the sequence of words.

The order of N-grams is determined by the value of n chosen [36], such as follows:

- *Unigram*: as defined by the author [36] is the sample language model form with which N equals one word or one character. by the following formula, each term is estimated independently.

$$p(w_1 w_2 \dots w_n) = p(w_i) \quad (1)$$

Otherwise:

$$P_{(unl)}(t_1 t_2 t_3) = P(t_1)P(t_2)P(t_3) \quad (2)$$

This shows that the terms $t_1 t_2 t_3$ are estimated independently, which means that the unigram method ignores the words' context.

- *Bigram*: Unlike unigram, the Bigram model adds a context word, and its conditions are on unigram terms:

$$p(w_i | w_1 w_2 \dots w_n) = p(w_i | w_{i-1}) \quad (3)$$

Otherwise:

$$p_{bi}(t_1 t_2 t_3) = p(t_1)p(t_2|t_1)p(t_3|t_2) \quad (4)$$

- *Trigram*: is more complex than bigrams and unigram, because its conditions are dependent on bigrams models terms, and adds two words to context.

$$p(w_i | w_1 w_2 \dots w_n) = p(w_i | w_{i-2} w_{i-1}) \quad (5)$$

Otherwise:

$$p_{tri}(t_1 t_2 t_3) = p(t_1)p(t_3|t_2)p(t_4|t_3|t_2) \quad (6)$$

Where:

$w_1 w_2 \dots w_n$ is a sequence of words;

$t_1 t_2 \dots t_n$ presents a sequence of terms;

P indicates the probability.

with the same formula above, the trigram and the four-grams are calculated.

In the proposed model for the classification process, we use four configuration stages given by [35] of n-grams such as (i) unigrams, (ii) bigrams (1g+2g), (iii) trigrams (1g+3g), and (iv) Fourgrams or (1g+4g), each one used with feature extraction TF-IDF. We see that the N-gram method divides sentences into small items like words, by looking at the length of n.

- TF-IDF: in natural language processing, the Term Frequency-Inverted Document Frequency (TF-IDF) is a weighting metric used to measure how important a term is to a document in a dataset [33]. Is the feature extraction method used to present the tokenized text by vectors useful for machine learning techniques.

The *tf-idf* weight assigned to the term t in a document d corresponds to the product of the term frequency tf and its inverse document frequency idf in the corpus.

4.4. Base Classifiers

- *Support Vector Machines (SVM)* is a machine learning technique used for natural language processing tasks like text classification, emotion detection, and image recognition [33]. The main objective is to find a hyperplane that best separates the data points of one class from those of others [37, 38]; The hyperplane built presents a large margin between classes.
- *Random Forest (RF)* according to the author [39]. RF is a machine learning technique for categorization tasks that consists of multiple decision trees prepared during the training phase; each tree is constructed by measuring a random subset of features in each division using a random subset of the dataset.
- *Logistic Regression (LR)* is an important classification technique used in predictive task analysis. It is a probabilistic model that uses the relationships between two factors to predict the value of one of them [40]; In fact, LR distinguishes classes based on the most significant learned features of the input [41].

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Model Training

The proposed models were implemented in Python using the Scikit-learn library on the Kaggle platform. The dataset was divided into a training set (80%) and a test set (20%) to evaluate classification performance across three categories: positive, negative, and neutral. Three classifiers were considered: Support Vector Machines (SVM), Logistic Regression (LR), and Random Forest (RF).

Models Testing results

This subsection presents the evaluation results of sentiment analysis models applied to the HASSANIYA dialect dataset. Following preprocessing and feature extraction using TF-IDF combined with n-grams, three machine learning classifiers were trained and tested. Model performance was assessed using key metrics, including F-measure, recall, and the area under the ROC curve (AUC).

The results are presented as follows: First, we provide an overview of the overall model performance on the test dataset. Next, we offer a detailed comparison of the classifiers based on evaluation metrics such as F-measure, recall, and AUC. Finally, we identify the best-performing model and demonstrate its applicability for

sentiment analysis use cases involving the HASSANIYA dialect.

Table 2 summarizes the evaluation results obtained with different TF-IDF feature configurations. Across all experiments, SVM model consistently outperformed LR and RF, achieving the highest accuracy of 63,14% with the multiple n-grams (1g+4g) and TF-IDF setting. followed closely by LR, reaching 62,57% under the same configuration, while RF obtained 58,28%. These results show a clear improvement compared to earlier stages, where unigram, bigram, and trigram features were used individually or in pairs. In those cases, the best accuracies were 61.14% for LR, 60.28% for SVM, and 57.71% for RF with the (1g+3g) configuration. By contrast, the lowest performance was observed with the unigram model alone. Overall, accuracy improved as multiple n-gram features were combined, underscoring the advantage of capturing broader contextual information.

Table 2: Models' Accuracy Results

Model	TF-IDF			
	Uni-gram	1g+2g	1g+3g	1g+4g
SVM	43.42%	58.57%	60.28%	63.14%
RF	45.71%	54.28%	57.71%	58.28%
LR	42.00%	57.14%	61.14%	62.57%

Table 3 summarizes the results of the evaluation metrics (F-score and recall) for the three classifiers. The models clearly show improvement, and the results indicate better performance when n-gram features are combined. For example, combining unigrams (1-grams) with 4-gram features yields around 60% for both F-score and recall for all three algorithms, compared to about 40% with unigrams alone and 50% with bigrams. This improvement underscores the importance of contextual information in sentiment analysis of the HASSANIYA dialect.

Table 3: Evaluation Metrics

Metric	Model	TF-IDF			
		Uni-gram	1g+2g	1g+3g	1g+4g
F-Score	SVM	0.42	0.58	0.60	0.63
	RF	0.43	0.56	0.54	0.55
	LR	0.42	0.57	0.61	0.62
Recall	SVM	0.43	0.59	0.60	0.63
	RF	0.45	0.57	0.55	0.56
	LR	0.42	0.57	0.61	0.63

The progressive improvement in accuracy, F-score, and recall when moving from unigrams to higher-order n-grams (bigrams, trigrams, and four-grams) confirms that sentiment in HASSANIYA often depends on short sequences of words rather than isolated terms.

In addition, the Area Under the Curve (AUC) metric is employed to evaluate classifier performance. Derived from the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve for each class, the AUC values range from 0.5 (equivalent to random guessing) to 1.0 (indicating perfect classification), as noted by [42]. We include AUC curves to compare model performance and to provide a more precise assessment of their effectiveness in classifying sentiment in HASSANIYA texts.

Using unigrams, the ROC curves Figure 4 indicate that the RF model outperforms the others across all classes, with AUC values reaching up to 70%. When bigrams are introduced, both the SVM and LR models show improved classification performance, surpassing RF, which does not exhibit a significant gain. With trigrams and 4-grams, SVM

and LR continue to improve their AUC scores for the Positive, Negative, and Neutral classes reaching up to 80% for the Positive and Neutral classes. In contrast, RF only shows a marginal improvement compared to its previous results, indicating limited benefit from higher-order n-gram features.

Although the reported performance remains moderate compared to state-of-the-art deep learning approaches applied to other Arabic dialects [6, 7, 18, 27], the findings confirm the feasibility of using traditional machine learning methods in low-resource settings. The relatively small size of the corpus and the linguistic complexity of the HASSANIYA dialect are likely factors that limited performance. Nevertheless, the consistent improvements observed with larger n-gram ranges suggest that capturing longer contextual dependencies can significantly enhance model effectiveness. Furthermore, integrating specific stemming, stop-words removal, and normalization produced notable gains, confirming the importance of text preprocessing in improving model accuracy.

Figure 4: ROC curves for different n-grams configurations

Exploring the results

Based on the experimental evaluation, SVM consistently achieved the best performance for sentiment classification in the HASSANIYA dialect and was therefore selected as the core model for downstream applications. An additional contribution of this study is the integration of the trained SVM into a prototype dashboard that visualizes sentiment distribution in real time. This dashboard illustrates the practical applicability of sentiment analysis for monitoring citizens' opinions on social media

platforms. By providing decision-makers with a clear overview of public attitudes, it demonstrates the potential of NLP techniques to support and strengthen e-government strategies in Mauritania.

Figure 5 shows an example of the proposed model's output after the preprocessing pipeline. The raw HASSANIYA comments are cleaned and normalized into processed text, which is then classified by the model into sentiment categories. In these examples, the predicted classes (Positive, Negative, Neutral) are correctly assigned

	comment_message	processed_text	predicted_sentiment
0	...أعلنت مديرية الامتحانات والمسابقات بوزارة التته	...أعلنت مديرية الامتحانات والمسابقات بوزارة التته	Neutral
1	♥ جزاكم الله بخير	جزاكم الله بخير	Positive
2	هههههه	هههههه	Positive
3	متابعين@	متابعين	Neutral
4	إشارة@	إشارة	Negative
5	مزينك يشي	مزينك يشي	Positive
6	ذو هل امبود؟	ذو هل امبود	Neutral

Figure 5: Example of model output

Figure 6: Output Sentiment over time

Figure 6 presents an example of tweet comments over time related to a post published on our test page used for model evaluation. The comments were posted between January 2025 and May 2025 and classified into three sentiment categories.

Prototype Dashboard for Decision Support

The best-performing model was integrated into a prototype interactive dashboard (Figure 7), designed by using Microsoft Power BI. This dashboard allows decision-makers to visualize the distribution of sentiments over time, filter by post, and assess overall satisfaction using key

performance indicators (KPIs). By providing an overview of citizens' reactions in near real time, the dashboard demonstrates the practical value of sentiment analysis as a tool to support e-government strategies in Mauritania and improve service delivery and strengthen public trust.

The main features of the dashboard include:

- Overall Sentiment Distribution:

Decision-makers can instantly visualize the percentage of positive, negative, and neutral feedback regarding a specific topic or time period. This sentiment indicator allows

decision-makers to quickly assess overall reactions to government initiatives.

- *Trends Over Time:* The evolution of public sentiment is shown graphically over several months, allowing the identification of changes that occurred before, during, and after specific events (such as public policy announcements or elections). The prototype illustrated citizen reactions from January to May 2025, revealing how sentiment shifted during the election period.
- *Filtering and Drill-down:* This feature allows government departments to focus on relevant comments regarding their

announcements and to analyze the data at different levels, from overall statistics to individual citizen comments, thus ensuring a comprehensive analysis of the feedback received.

- *Key Performance Indicators (KPIs):* The dashboard includes summary indicators such as the number of analyzed comments, the overall sentiment score (difference between positive and negative comments), and identification of trending topics based on text analysis.

Figure 7: Dashboard of classified sentiment

From an application perspective, the implementation of the sentiment-analysis system provides valuable insights into citizens’ perceptions of public services. By classifying and aggregating online comments, decision-makers can monitor satisfaction trends and identify emerging issues based on citizens’ opinions. This demonstrates the practical value of sentiment analysis as a decision-support tool, thereby confirming the feasibility of the initial research hypothesis.

6. LIMITATIONS

In this study, we observed that the TF-IDF implemented with n-gram has limitations in extracting the root of the HASSANIYA word and subsequently has limitations in identifying sentiments. Unlike results reported for Tunisian dialect

sentiment analysis [27], where machine learning techniques achieved higher performance. The issue related to the effectiveness of this method in Mauritania dialect classification is the availability of a large dataset. The scarcity of annotated data for the HASSANIYA dialect, combined with the complex morphology and lack of standardized linguistic resources, appears to be the main factors behind this limitation.

Since the model’s performance is influenced by the limited size of the current dataset and its linguistic particularities, future work should expand and diversify the corpus and reapply the feature-extraction techniques to achieve more reliable and generalizable results. Additionally, in this case study, the proposed model was evaluated using the Facebook Graph API, which restricted access to page comments only. To build more

comprehensive and representative models, future studies should explore alternative data collection methods or publicly accessible APIs to gather a wider range of user-generated content across multiple social media platforms.

7. CONCLUSION

This study highlights the potential of sentiment analysis for the HASSANIYA dialect in social media as a means to strengthen the effectiveness of online government services and foster closer engagement between citizens and decision-makers. Despite the scarcity of HASSANIYA resources, we implemented a machine learning approach that enabled the monitoring of citizens' comments. The results confirm the feasibility of employing sentiment analysis as a tool to support and improve public service delivery. For future work, we recommend expanding the dataset and exploring state-of-the-art transformer-based models developed for Arabic, which are likely to achieve greater effectiveness.

Data Availability Statement: The original data presented in the study are openly available at Zenodo:

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